

Project Citizen Digital: Education In The Era Of Industrial Revolution 4.0

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 25, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: October 23, 2020</p> <p>Keywords Project Citizen Digital, Education 4.0, teacher competence, 21st Century Skills</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4121176</p>	<p><i>This study aims to develop a project citizen digital learning model as an alternative educational solution in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0. Project Citizen Digital is a digital-based application of the project citizen learning model which has positive implications for the development of students' competence as citizens in the global era. This research is a design-based research development (Research and Development) using the SDLC model waterfall software development procedure. The waterfall stage includes problem analysis, product design, coding, and testing. From this research, a project citizen digital application is produced and used as a learning medium for Pancasila and civic education. The results of this study indicate that the project citizen digital learning model is an alternative educational solution in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0. These results also demand teachers in this revolutionary era to have competences in teaching and educating, media literacy, globalization, future strategies, technology-friendly attitude, collaboration, and holistic teaching.</i></p>

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the world has entered the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 marked by increased connectivity and interaction, as well as the development of digital, artificial intelligence, and virtual systems. This revolution shift affects all elements of human life starting from behavior, use of communication tools, and technology-based education (Lasi et al, 2014, Lase, 2019, Mcphee, et al, 2017; Wagner, et al, 2017;). Changes in this era cannot be avoided so that adequate preparation of human resources (HR) is needed to be ready to adapt and compete on a global scale as well as understanding technology holistically (Lewin&Mcnicol, 2014; Mayes, Natividad, & Spector, 2015). Improving the quality of human resources through education from primary and secondary education to higher education is the key to being able to keep up with the development of the Industrial Revolution 4.0.

All systems in the world of education must be transformed from traditional to modern systems (Xu, David, & Kim, 2018) since the industrial revolution 4.0 demands education to produce graduates with good skills and global competitive abilities to improve their quality (Dwiyanti, Ana, &Widianingsih, 2018; Hariharasudan&Kot, 2018). Transforming the teacher-centered teaching into a digital learning model using varied and fun media is one of the efforts to prepare the education system to produce competitive graduates. As digital natives who grew up with digital technology (Sailin, Mahmor, 2018), students in the current generation can understand technology because they rapidly and sophisticatedly process the information (Venter, 2016; Bolton, et.al, 2013). Menurut Prensky, M (2001) Therefore, they are confident in using new technologies such as the internet, video games, cellular technology, YouTube, and other digital tools.

The changes of education system around the world happened rapidly, in line with the rapid changes of technology, make thorough preparations to meet the 21st-century learning expectations of digital natives. The 21st-century was marked by the collaboration of accelerated access of technology and information (Faheem et al., 2018, Sardone et al., 2010). Partnership for 21st Century Learning (2015) stated that the 21st-century students must be able to master science and technology to communicate, use information, solve problems, and think critically since being creative, critical, and able to solve problems are the main abilities of 21st century (Laar, Deursen, Dijk, & Haan, 2017; Rahman, 2019). The Center for Civic Education (CCE) states that critical thinking skills include several elements such as the ability to identify, describe and explain, evaluate, argue, defend opinions, and listen (CCE, 2004). Therefore, project citizen learning is suitable to be applied in the 21st century considering the application of the critical approach and problem-solving approach in this model. Besides, this learning model requires students to critically understand the case or problem that is being studied as well as finding alternative solutions to the problem.

Budimansyah (2009) explains, "Project Citizen is an instructional treatment in the form of problem-based learning activities (social issues or problems) aiming to develop knowledge, skills, disposition of democratic and participative citizens, and civilized civil society." The learning process with the citizenship project model is very suitable to be applied in a functioning Civic Education subject to shape the intelligence, skills, and character of citizens. However, to be able to integrate technology into teaching practice in education

in the era of industrial revolution 4.0, a digital-based project citizen model is needed in the form of an application which facilitates not only face-to-face but also online learning which results in a product (Garcia, 2017, Helle, et.al, 2006, Choi et.al 2019)

Based on the description above, the industrial revolution 4.0 marked by technology has significant implications for the education system. The question is, how can the development of a project citizen digital learning model be an alternative solution for education in the industrial revolution 4.0? This paper aims to explain the project citizen digital application that needs to be conducted in the education system to respond to the digital revolution so that educational output can compete and contribute globally.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Project Citizen Digital

Civic education learning practice is an innovative learning model to improve students' understanding of citizenship theory through practical learning experience that provides students' training in contextual learning (Depdiknas, 2003). Meanwhile, according to Budimansyah (2009), project citizen is a model for developing students' civic skills, knowledge, and disposition that encourage active participation in society and government.

Budimansyah (2008) also emphasizes that the premise of Project Citizen lies in a framework consisting of five parts on the idea of education and politics. First, it requires the involvement of citizens in the citizens' life. Second, the essence of Civic Education is the value when students take an active part in citizen life. Third, by exploring the problems that exist in their communities, they will understand the principles of democracy which are the core of citizenship knowledge. Fourth, project citizen is included to be applied especially by middle school students or early adolescents (aged around 10-15 years) who have experienced a shift from concrete thinking to abstract thinking. Fifth, project citizen regards students as a source of citizenship whose ideas and energies can be devoted to issues of public policy.

According to Budimansyah and Suryadi (2008), the instructional strategy used in this model is based on inquiry, discovery, problem-solving, and research-oriented learning strategies which are packaged in the John Dewey project model. In addition, to citizenship knowledge, Project Citizen aims to assist in the development of various citizenship skills that are essential for the implementation of democratic citizenship. In project citizen activities, students have many opportunities to apply intellectual and aspirational skills, develop civic character such as politics (values, interests, tolerance), commitment to the implementation of democratic citizenship rights, constitutionalism, and the tendency to participate politically.

Furthermore, the project citizen learning model also focuses on educating students, as young citizens, to be able to analyze various dimensions of public policy and provide input regarding the public policies applied in their environment. Therefore, it is expected that this model will result in the development of citizens who are smart, creative, participative, prospective, and responsible.

Besides the explanation about project citizen above, project citizen digital has positive implications for the development of students' competence as citizens in the global era. Digital-based learning in the form of application will produce an active learning process and stimulate students to have creative and critical thinking skills because students are challenged to compare and respond to their and other people's ideas using the digital application (Davies & Merchant, 2007; Richardson, 2009; Sailin & Mahmor, 2017).

Industrial Revolution Education 4.0

The concept of the industrial revolution 4.0 was first introduced by Klaus Schwab through his book, *The Fourth Industrial Revolution*, which states that the industrial revolution 4.0 can fundamentally change the way we live, work, and relate to one another. According to Halim (2018), there are four stages of the industrial revolution. First, the industrial revolution took place at the end of the 18th century which is marked by the discovery of the first mechanical loom in 1784. Second, the industrial revolution 2.0 took place in the early 20th century with the introduction of mass production based on the division of labor. Third, the early 1970s are considered to be the first time the industrial revolution 3.0 began with the use of electronics and information technology to automate production. Finally, 2018 until now is the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 that combines technology automation with cyber technology resulting in a trend of automation and data exchange in manufacturing technology. In this era, the industry has begun to touch the virtual world in the form of a human, machine, data connectivity, and the Internet of Things (IoT) in which everything is already everywhere.

The Industrial Revolution 4.0, started in the 2000s, placed automation in a dominant position and moved between physical production systems and cyberspace which work hand in hand and overlap in large part with advances in the technology known as the Smart Factory, the Industrial Internet of Things, the Smart Industry, or Advanced Manufacturing (Kinzel, 2012). Industry 4.0 is a combination of several of the latest advanced technologies such as physical cyber system, communication and information technology, big data, modelling, simulation, virtualisasi, and cooperation (Kinzel, 2012).

Human beings and technology are coordinated to creatively and innovatively create new opportunities for facing the education 4.0. According to Fisk (2017), there are nine trends related to education 4.0, namely learning at different times and places, individual learning, student choices in determining how they learn,

project-based learning, field experiences, data interpretation, diverse assessments, student involvement, and a shift in education 4.0 trends.

The nine shifts in education 4.0 trends above are the main responsibility of teachers to students. Therefore, educators must play a role to support the transition and not perceive it as a threat to conventional teaching which is indeed an exciting, action-provoking, and a massive challenge. Adaptation to this educational trend guarantees individuals and communities to develop a more complete set of competencies, skills, and knowledge as well as unleash their full creative potential.

METHODS

This research is a design-based research development that is used to develop and validate effective products for school use instead of theory testing. Development research design only validates products and produces product prototypes not to test theories. In this research, the product is a project citizen digital.

This study aims to produce a product, understand its validity and practicality, leaving understanding the impact of the product. The product produced in this study is a "project citizen digital" learning application, so the method used is the system development method or SDLC (System Development Life Cycle). SDLC is a classic methodology used to develop, maintain, and use information systems (Kadir, 2015) which includes a number of phases or stages. Basically, every SDLC development model has the same cycle with the SDLC waterfall development model as the simplest and is suitable for software development with unchanging specifications (Rosa and Shalahuddin, 2014). Therefore, the development model used in this study is the SDLC waterfall. The following is a chart of the waterfall development procedure in this study.

1. Analysis Stage

This test aims to improve the project citizen digital application by using it as a learning medium. The tests carried out are alpha testing and beta testing. Alpha testing was carried out by 3 media experts and 3 material experts, meanwhile, beta testing was carried out twice. The first beta testing was conducted on 3 class XI IPS students of SMA Negeri 21 Bandung. The selection of trial subjects is based on data on the types of favorite applications according to students to determine the tendency of students to respond to applications. The student consists of a game fan, a social media fan, and a learning application fan. The second beta testing in this

study was applied to one class, namely the XI IPS class, provided that no student in that class had ever taken the first beta testing.

The data collection instrument is divided into two categories, namely pre-research and research. The pre-research instrument included an interview guideline and an instrument for conceptual understanding while the research instruments include the appraisal scale for the appropriateness of the project citizen digital and the assessment scale for the practicality of the project citizen digital. This feasibility assessment will determine whether this project citizen digital is valid or not. On the other hand, the project citizen digital practicality rating scale will state whether the project citizen digital is practical or not. The qualitative data input was processed and analyzed descriptively-qualitatively while the qualitative data on the checklist sheet was converted into numbers.

FINDINGS

The results obtained from the making process of the project citizen digital application are as follows.

1. Analysis Stage

At the stage of analyzing the product to be developed, it was found that SMA Negeri 21 Bandung is a school that has implemented digital learning which is feasible to be engaged for product testing. The class chosen is class XI IPS considering the availability of the mobile devices that students have. At this stage, the authors distributed a questionnaire to find out the operating system on students' smartphones which resulted in 88.7% of 25 students use an Android operating system that is automatically chosen as the operating system in this development. Furthermore, the authors conducted a problem analysis consisting of teachers' needs and students' characteristics, curriculum, and material. From this analysis, it was known that there is a need to develop the project citizen digital as a learning medium in facing the industrial revolution 4.0 education. This is supported by the results of interviews which show that teachers have difficulty in delivering material online in the corona pandemic condition so that they require project-based digital learning media. The results of the preliminary study on concept understanding showed that students need to be facilitated since the students' academic achievement was only 52% while the minimum good academic achievement criterion is at least 60%. Furthermore, the authors conducted a system analysis by obtaining information about the project citizen digital to be developed, namely designing a project citizen digital as a medium for learning civic education based on a contextual approach to facilitate conceptual understanding.

2. Design (Planning Stage)

The preparation of the product requirement map is carried out based on curriculum and material analysis. This preparation includes the collection of material in the form of a word-format document integrated with a contextual approach to facilitate conceptual understanding. The authors continue by compiling a display design using Corel Draw X7 (graphic design software); turquoise, white, and gray as the basic colors and black as the font color. Furthermore, the authors compile a quality assessment instrument for project citizen digital based on product quality achievement criteria, namely valid and practical. Additionally, the authors validate to determine the validity or accuracy of the instrument to measure the quality of the developed project citizen digital.

3. Coding Stage

The coding phase for project citizen digital begins with preparing all its components followed by building project citizen digital pages consisting of 6 pages. The authors built pages one by one and input the content through the drag and drop method. The authors do coding (compiling commands with a programming language, namely HTML) on the quiz page and the timer page. After the pages of project citizen digital are put together, the next step is to try to operate the project citizen digital via a computer or laptop. This step was followed by building the digital form or apk file as Draft 1 which was then tested by the supervisor. Since Draft 1 still has shortcomings, at this stage, the supervisor provides input as an effort to perfect Draft 1. The revised products are called Draft 2 of project citizen digital equipped with an A5-sized user manual book which was prepared as a guide for using project citizen digital.

4. Testing Stage

a) Alpha Testing

The results of the project citizen digital assessment are described in the table below.

1). Quality assessment of Project Citizen Digital by material experts

Table 1. Results of Project Citizen Digital Quality Assessment by Media Experts

No.	Evaluator	Component Assessment Results				Total
		Material Coverage	Material Accuracy	Contextuality	Facilitating Concept Understanding	
1	I	20	22	26	27	95
2	II	19	24	25	26	94
3	III	20	22	27	24	93

Total	59	68	78	77	282
Mean	19.7	22.6	26	25.6	94
Percentage	98%	94%	92%	91%	93%
Category	Very Good				

2). Media member evaluation components

Table 2. Result of Quality Assessment of Project Citizen Digital by MediaExperts

No.	Evaluator	Component Assessment Results				Total
		Presentation	Appearance	Software Engineering	Implementation	
1	I	30	41	8	15	94
2	II	30	45	8	16	99
3	III	28	40	7	16	91
Total		88	126	23	47	284
Mean		29.3	42	7.7	15.7	15
Percentage		92%	95%	96%	98%	95%
Category		Very Good	Very Good	Very Good	Very Good	Very Good

From the results of all assessments, it was found that all components fall into very good category both from media experts and material experts so it could be concluded that the Project Citizen Digital application developed was valid and could be continued to the next stage. The revised Draft 2 hereinafter referred to as Draft 3.

b). Beta Testing

Beta testing was carried out twice. The first beta test was conducted by taking students' responses to the developed Project Citizen Digital application which was carried out on February 10, 2020. Based on input from the three students, in general, they responded positively to Draft 3 regarding readability and design. The second beta test was carried out on May 14, 2020. In terms of its use by students, the assessment results of the Project Citizen Digital application show the average score of 3.7 from the ideal maximum score of 4. So that students' responses to the project citizen digital application fall into the Agree category.

DISCUSSION

Project Citizen equips students with a pleasant learning atmosphere, provides experiences, and increases students' knowledge. The steps for learning Project Citizen cannot be separated from the acceleration of globalization and the development of information and technology in the industrial era 4.0. In the industrial era 4.0, teachers and students balance learning activities between direct and online interaction with society. Research by Adha et al (2019) shows that the Project Citizen learning model applies the development of information and technology to support learning outcomes optimally and in accordance with current developments. The use of sophisticated devices that are connected to internet connectivity is one component for exploring data and information that supports the material being discussed in the classroom. Project Citizen always provides opportunities for students to apply advanced technology tools and gather information online. However, collecting data and information through discussions and interviews is still an important factor for students.

The Project Citizen learning model is designed to provide students with experience in developing citizen attitudes based on three components of democratic citizenship, namely 1) civic knowledge; 2) civic skills; and 3) civic dispositions (Vontz et al., 2000). The development of information and technology, especially in the industrial era 4.0, must be supported by the quality of citizens who are smart, creative, participatory, prospective, and responsible. Project Citizen aims for students to develop positively and democratically especially in the acceleration of the industrial 4.0 era by maximizing the use of relevant learning resource applications. Learning resources and student activities are guided by the fact that students' actions and group work are to form virtuous students living in mutual cooperation (social cohesion). Therefore, the right model to be applied in the current era of the industrial revolution 4.0 is Project Citizen Digital.

The Project Citizen Digital model is an application that facilitates the implementation of project citizen through e-learning. First, the application is downloaded using their respective cellphones, then students, teachers, and judges log in to the application, as shown below:

Figure 5. Log In Display of Project Citizen Digital

After logging into the application, the teachers, students, and judges input their identity including name, school, class, then proceed to the system to carry out the learning process which begins with attendance and conversation. Project Citizen Digital consists of 6 steps, namely:

1. Identifying Problem. In this first step, the teacher provides explanations or directions to students to write down problem topics that are around the student's environment or in society by providing problem examples that can be downloaded in the application. The problem identification is typed by the student in the application and is not limited to writing the topic, every student has the same opportunity. A number of problem identification lists can be seen and considered by students before entering the second step of this model. Essentially, the identification of problems written by students in the project citizen digital application is a problem that students think needs to be studied and sought solutions. After the problem identification has been written by the students, then students can proceed to the second step.

2. Choosing a class study material problem. The second step of the project citizen digital model is selecting problems to be used as study material or themes discussed by the group. One by one, students vote in the application on one of the topics they choose/want. After the students have finished voting to choose the main topic/theme to be used as a classroom study, the teacher and the students calculate the number of votes from each problem identification list in the system. The problem with the largest number of votes was used as material for class study, then each student prepared the information needed to develop a portfolio.

3. Gathering Information. The third step is to collect information and other supporting data needed for discussion and analysis materials that will be attached to cardboard for group viewing and digital projects that will be displayed on the application. Students can find information from books in the library, newspapers, office employees, the internet, interviews with resource persons, and other sources of information that can be obtained by students while in the field. When students conduct interviews, students can interview their parents, siblings, heads of RT/RW, government office employees, and other sources related to the themes studied by students. The collection of information carried out by students based on the time set by the teacher, the materials and information collected were compiled by the students to be used when entering the fourth step, namely making the material presentation or portfolio. The information collected at this stage is intended so that the class can obtain accurate and comprehensive information. The portfolio will be divided into two parts: an impression section and a documentation section.

4. Creating a class portfolio. Portfolios or presentation materials made by students at this stage require student cooperation to produce a good portfolio supported by descriptions of information that answer the problems and studies discussed. The class will be divided into four groups, each group has a different role (which will be described in the portfolio group section). The materials in the form of data and information that have been collected by students are then arranged and made with the creativity of each group to be affixed to cardboard. The students wrote documentation affixed to cardboard in the form of descriptions, diagrams, statistical data, pictures or photos, and interview results. The portfolio is approximately 90x100 cm in size, and a class study theme/topic is written which is placed at the top of the portfolio after all group portfolios are combined first. The portfolio itself is divided into two parts, namely the impression section (cardboard) and the documentation section (information material that is put in a folder and placed on the front of the cardboard portfolio). Portfolios are not only on cardboard but displayed on the monitor when presenting. Class portfolio group assignments are divided into four, namely:

- a. Portfolio Group One: Describe the Problem
- b. Portfolio Group Two: Assess alternative policies suggested to solve the problem
- c. Portfolio Group Three: develop public policies

d. Portfolio Group Four: develop a work plan

5. Presenting Portfolio in front of the Judges. After the portfolios have been prepared by the students, the students get ready to present the material of their respective groups in front of the judges, the invitees, and other students who attended. This portfolio presentation can be called a showcase. This stage provides opportunities for students to express ideas and results of the analysis that have been carried out. Here students learn to be brave to present a material or concept in front of the judges and guests. The presentation must be able to give confidence to the invitees that the arguments and policies taken by the students are the results of good analysis and decisions for society in the future.

The activity (showcase) is the pinnacle of students' performance because, at this stage, the results of student work will be tested and debated in front of the judges. The purpose of the portfolio presentation is to convey the results of the discussion to the invitees and students as an important matter to be studied by bringing alternative solutions offered to the community. At this stage, students present several perspectives from an alternative policy that has an impact on society. Besides, in the portfolio presentation section, students discuss with the audience that the chosen policy is the best policy to deal with these problems. Furthermore, students must also be able to make a rational argument to support their thinking and the policy chosen does not conflict with the 1945 Constitution. Portfolio presentations also aim to get the class to get support from the public, legislative and executive bodies, government, or private institutions for class choice policies.

6. Reflecting on learning experiences. This stage is carried out after a series of portfolio presentations. Students are then invited to reflect (take lessons or benefits from the showcase activity), evaluate, give their opinion both about the material being studied and input for the implementation of similar activities that will be carried out in the future. In this process, of course, students are expected to achieve learning outcomes that are beneficial to themselves personally. Students can convey several things that have been achieved and are useful for students during their reflection in the classroom, such as 1) increased knowledge of public policy concepts or studies; 2) more information-densely developed portfolios based on students' knowledge of public policy; 3) better practical skills after going through the process of being involved in the project; 4) getting the benefits when they work in groups and comprehensive discussion results; 5) ability to identify things or activities that can hinder group work when completing the portfolio; 6) ability to evaluate the results of their achievements and group work; 7) getting trained to find alternative solutions in solving problems both around students and society; 8) ability to think that the implementation of each stage in this project will have similarities and differences in the process of working in the field.

CONCLUSION

Project Citizen Digital is a digital-based application of the project citizen learning model which has positive implications for the development of students' competence as citizens in the global era. Project citizen digital facilitating understanding of the concept has met the criteria for achieving product quality, namely valid and practical. Favorably, project citizen digital was declared valid by material experts with an ideal percentage of 93% and by media experts with an ideal percentage of 95%. In addition, the application of project citizen digital was also stated as practical by students with an ideal percentage of 90%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the project citizen digital learning model is an alternative educational solution in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0

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